

**Impact of time demands of work on job satisfaction and turnover intention: Software developers
in offshore outsourced software development firms in Sri Lanka**

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Purpose- The purpose of this study was to examine the mediating effect of job satisfaction on the relationship between time demands of work and turnover intention of software developers in offshore outsourced software development firms (OOSDF) in Sri Lanka.

Design/methodology/approach- Survey research methodology was used and 232 software developers attached to OOSDF responded.

Findings- It was found that job satisfaction partially mediates the relationship between time demands of work and turnover intention.

Research limitations/implications- The results of the questionnaire survey provided access to breadth of experience. If qualitative data were also obtained those could have been provided depth by adding insight and substance to the questionnaire survey.

Practical implications- The findings imply that a greater understanding of employee turnover intentions might be gained by investigating the time demands of work.

Originality/value- It is expected that the findings of this study will provide useful information for both practitioners and academics to better understand the nature of strategies to be adopted in Asian OOSDF.

Keywords: time demands of work; turnover intention; job satisfaction; offshore outsourcing; software development, Sri Lanka.

Paper: Research paper

Introduction

Software developers involve in producing information technology (IT) related output as his or her primary job function (SLICTA, 2007, p.7). Scholarios and Marks (2004) suggest that the high level of occupational identification among software developers is suggestive of a new or aspirant profession and designate them as the key occupation to examine in future studies

of knowledge workers. It is also suggested that software developers enjoy a considerable labour market power, which has encouraged their mobility across organisations rather than promoting loyalty to a single organisation (Cappelli, 2001; Scholarios and Marks, 2004).

During the last decade Sri Lanka witnessed a growth of OOSDF in the country. Sri Lanka's offshore outsourcing sector emerged in the mid 1990s and currently has approximately a 30,000 member IT workforce of which 45% have a Bachelor's degree or a higher qualification in IT (SLICTA, 2007). They could be identified as one of the critical resources of the country in its quest to become a technologically advanced nation. However, specific literature on the work environment of employees engaged in the offshore software development sector is limited compared to the literature available on the work environment of employees engaged in IT enabled services (ITES) sector of the country (e.g. LIRNEasia, 2006; SLICTA, 2007; Wickramasinghe, 2009; Wickramasinghe and Kumara, 2010).

However, specific literature on software developers attached to offshore outsourced software development industry in the South Asian context provides evidence for both extensive opportunities created for IT personnel (Arun and Arun, 2002; D'Mello, 2006; Wickramasinghe, 2009) as well as increased stress in the workplace (Aziz, 2004). Despite the growing amount of interest to understand IT workforce issues in the context of Asian offshore outsourcing industry among academics and practitioners, there appears to be paucity of direct empirical data on software development sector in the South Asian context.

Further, the literature emphasises the importance of examining the meaning of work in the lives of employed people of the knowledge intensive sectors, where economic value is found more in intangibles and less in tangibles (e.g. Hyman et al., 2003). Specifically, scholars suggest that the attitudes of software developers towards the characteristics of work organisation in the offshore outsourced sector have, as yet, not been systematically examined (e.g. Scholarios and Marks, 2004). This paper considers "working time" as a factor in analyzing work and the workplace of software developers attached to OOSDF in Sri Lanka. Given the interest in society concerning workforce related issues in offshore outsourced context, software developers' attitudes towards the time demands of work and its

influence on job satisfaction, and in turn on their decisions to stay or leave the offshore outsourced software development profession appear to be a candidate for increased theoretical and empirical attention.

In the above context, the purpose of this paper is to present and discuss the results of an empirical study that investigated the relationship between time demands of work, job satisfaction and turnover intention. Specifically, by taking into account how time demands of work affects job satisfaction and how job satisfaction in turn impacts on employees' turnover intention, the study tested the role of job satisfaction as a mediator between time demands of work and turnover intention (refer to Figure 1).

In order to provide context for this article, in the next section, relevant literature is briefly reviewed. This is followed by the methodology adopted. Thereafter, the main findings are presented and discussed. The article concludes with a discussion on the implications of the findings and research areas for further inquiry and understanding.

Theoretical background and hypotheses

The literature suggests that individuals in organisations enact formally prescribed work related duties and responsibilities to be good organisational citizens (Welbourne et al., 1998). However, literature also suggests that employees often find difficulties to engage in work roles in the light of the time available, their abilities, and other constraints (Perlow, 1998). That is fulfilling work roles is likely to require additional resources on the part of employees, particularly in terms of their time and energy. When employees struggle to find time and resources needed to satisfactorily complete their in-role responsibilities, they may bring things home to work on, stay at work after normal business hours, work on their days-offs, and so forth in order to get the job done (Bolino and Turnley, 2005; Hyman et al., 2003). Therefore, scholars identify "time" as a factor in analysing work and the workplace (Epstein and Kalleberg, 2001).

Epstein and Kalleberg (2001, p. 5) state that "how much time people should spend at work is supported by cultural traditions that have permitted and forbidden work at various

times and are shaped by powerful individuals and groups who have required and persuaded individuals to work according to their dictates". Further, conventions regarding working time have been constrained by realities such as season, the length of day and night, and the physical limits of human capacity (Epstein and Kalleberg, 2001, p. 5). In this regard, Wise et al. (2007) provide evidence that technology help tele-nursing employees to achieve a better work-life balance with compared to traditional face-to-face nursing by facilitating a greater employee control over working time. In offshore outsourced work environment, the use of technology has altered the boundaries of space and distance facilitating employees to work, however, subjection to the wishes of the organisation. Therefore, offshore outsourced work environment demands a kind of time commitment of their employees (refer to Perlow, 2001).

Although organisations in a given industry tend to take on similar norms and practices resulting in a subset of work experiences that can be observed across various organisational contexts in that particular industry, Perlow (2001) provides evidence of software developers working in India, China, and Hungary who perform the same kind of work for the same international corporation but subjected to work environments in which time expectations vary substantially. According to Perlow (2001), Chinese software developers work in a highly regulated and time-defined standard workday. In India, software developers are expected to work long hours if necessary and to work weekends as well, appearing on Saturdays whether there is work to do or not. In Hungary, hours are the most flexible, with software developers coming in late, leaving early, and working from home, working overtime only in times of great necessity. Based on the observations, Perlow (2001) suggests that it is not because of technology that individuals are driven to ever increasing hours of work in the offshore outsourced software development industry; the most important factor in determining workplace schedules is management. Therefore, Perlow (2001) argues that alterations in the nature of management, and different ideas about how to work, could develop different work settings although the work itself is the same.

Understanding such perceptions is important as past studies provide evidence that time demands of work may influence individuals' work related attitudes (e.g. Livingstone and

Stowe, 2007; Müller and Wyss, 2007; Skinner and Pocock, 2008). For instance, it was found that time demands of work influence job satisfaction (e.g. Skinner and Pocock, 2008; Thornthwaite 2004; Wallace 1997). Further, a low level of job satisfaction has been linked to an increased turnover intent and actual turnover among employees (e.g. Byrd et al., 2000). Furthermore, in a study conducted to assess the implications of atypical forms of working hours on employees' leisure and social activities, Müller and Wyss (2007) suggest that the extent to which working hours can be planned exert a definite influence on the functioning of social environment. Further, Livingstone and Stowe (2007) suggest that working time influences employees' participation in work-related learning activities.

In the Sri Lankan context, Wickramasinghe (2009) also suggests that work environment of offshore IT industry influences job satisfaction of IT employees, which in turn may influence their turnover intention. Further, Wickramasinghe and Kumara (2010) provide evidence that employees engaged in the ITES sector (which does not include software development) have relatively more negative perceptions towards their working hours and perceive relatively high work exhaustion. However, it should be noted that the employees engaged in the ITES sector are not considered as IT employees because their main job function does not involve producing IT related output although they use IT in their day-to-day work (SLICTA, 2007, p.7). Therefore, there is a need to examine the time demands of work experienced by the software developers employed in the offshore outsourced context and whether the time demands of work influence their feeling of job satisfaction and in turn influence their decisions to stay or leave the industry.

Overall, the review of specific literature on working time of the offshore software development sector (e.g. Perlow, 2001), ITES sector (e.g. Wickramasinghe and Kumara, 2010) as well as literature, in general, on working time (e.g. Skinner and Pocock, 2008; Thornthwaite 2004; Wallace 1997) suggests that working time influences employees' work related attitudes. Further, specific literature on the influence of job satisfaction as a mediator between the time demands of work and turnover intention is very rare to be found.

Therefore, drawing from the above reviewed literature, following hypotheses are proposed for this study:

Hypothesis 1. Time demands of work will be positively related to turnover intention

Hypothesis 2. Time demands of work will be negatively related to job satisfaction

Hypothesis 3. Job satisfaction will be negatively related to turnover intention

Hypothesis 4. Job satisfaction will mediate the relationship between time demands of work and turnover intention

Figure 1 illustrates the proposed relationships.

Take in Figure 1

Methodology

Sample

A random sample of software developers full-time engaged in OOSDF was selected. The list of software development firms registered and operate under Board of Investment of Sri Lanka (BOI) was used as BOI is the government authority responsible for identifying, promoting and facilitating export-oriented business operations in the country through both foreign and local investments. Further, it is compulsory by BOI Act (No.4 of 1978) that all BOI registered firms should export at least 90 percent of their output. Therefore, BOI registered software development firms provide at least 90 per cent of their work for offshore client firms. By the end of 2008 there were about 36 firms that were engaged purely in software development. At the second stage, a contact person was identified at each firm. This person was asked to randomly identify respondents whose main job function is software development from his/her firm and distribute the self-administered survey questionnaire. Of the 350 questionnaires sent out, 232 valid responses were returned, yielding a response rate of 66 per cent of the original sample.

With regard to demographics of the respondents, 66% were male and 44% were female. 47% were single and 53% were married. The mean age was 30 years (SD=2.86; min.= 27 years; max.=40 years). The average number of years of service in the present firm was 3 years (SD=1.55; min=11 months; max=7 years); the average number of years of service in the IT industry was 7 years (SD=1.94; min.= 11 months; max.=11 years). 83% had Bachelors degrees or equivalent professional qualifications such as Membership in British Computer Society, Australian Computer Society, and Project Management Professional; 17% had postgraduate degrees. 82% reported that they did not have dependents.

Measures

Independent, dependent and mediator variables were measured using a five-point Likert response scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). For all measurement scales, standardised Cronbach's alpha was examined and Principal-components factor analysis (Varimax rotation) was conducted. The criteria adhered to are: Eigenvalues of all components should not be less than 1.0; the loadings should be 0.50 or greater to be considered practically significant; cronbach's alpha values of each factor extracted and overall measure should be greater than 0.7 (see Hair et al., 2006). The items of each factor were averaged to produce a mean score for the each construct (refer to Table I).

Time demands of work was measured by the three items of "Usually I work more hours, some times until late in the night", "Usually I come to work on week ends, sometimes both Saturday and Sunday", and "Usually I take office work home when I leave the office, which I couldn't complete during the day". Factor analysis yielded one factor, where standardised Cronbach's alpha=.70 Eigenvalue=2.08, Explained variation=63.0%.

Job satisfaction was measured by the six items from Rusbult and Farrell (1983). Example items include "All things considered, I am extremely satisfied with my current assignments and responsibilities" and "My current work compares very well to my ideal job". Factor analysis yielded one factor, where standardised Cronbach's alpha=.875 Eigenvalue=2.39, Explained variation=79.95%.

Turnover intention was measured by the four items from Bluedorn (1982). Example items include “I often think about quitting” and “It is likely that I will actively look for a new job next year”. A higher value indicates a higher level of quitting intention. Factor analysis yielded one factor, where standardised Cronbach’s alpha=.755 Eigenvalue=2.02, Explained variation=67.45%.

The literature suggests that individuals’ perceptions may vary by their demographic characteristics (e.g. Kossek et al., 1999; Lim and Teo, 1999). Therefore, three individual demographic characteristics were controlled in the analysis. These variables are gender (female=0, male=1), marital status (single=0, married=1), and the years of experience in the present workplace (continuous scale).

Data analysis procedure

Regression analysis was used to test the hypotheses. The three-step procedure recommended by Baron and Kenny (1986) was used to test the mediation hypothesis. According to Baron and Kenny (1986), the following conditions must be met to support a mediating relationship. First, the independent variable must be significantly associated with the dependent variable. Second, the independent variable must be significantly associated with the mediator. Finally, after the mediator is entered, the relationship between the independent and dependent variables should either disappear (full mediation) or significantly diminish (partial mediation). In addition to the above conditions set out by Baron and Kenny (1986), Preacher and Leonardelli’s (2001) interactive programme was used to calculate critical ratios. To confirm the nature of the mediation relationship (full or partial), Jose’s (2004) Excel version of MedGraph programme was used.

Results

Table I shows means and standard deviations for time demands of work.

Take in Table I

Table II shows means, standard deviations and zero-order correlations between all the variables. As can be seen in Table II, the time demands of work is positively related to turnover intention while negatively related to job satisfaction. Job satisfaction is negatively related to turnover intention.

Take in Table II

In analysing the mediator effect of job satisfaction, the hypotheses were tested by estimating a series of multiple regression equations following the procedure presented in the section on “data analysis procedure”. The results are shown in Table III. As can be seen in Table III, the conditions for mediation were met. Time demands of work significantly positively associated with turnover intention supporting H1. Time demands of work significantly negatively associated with job satisfaction supporting H2. Job satisfaction significantly negatively related to turnover intention supporting H3. After job satisfaction is entered, the relationship between time demands of work and turnover intention significantly diminishes ($\beta=.376$, $p<.001$ to $\beta=.222$, $p<.01$), suggesting partial mediation. Critical ratios obtained from Preacher and Leonardelli’s (2001) interactive programme are also shown in Table III. In addition, standardised coefficients of time demands of work on turnover intention revealing direct and indirect effects obtained from Jose’s (2004) MedGraph programme are also shown in Table III. Accordingly, the mediation hypothesis (H4) that job satisfaction mediates the relationship between time demands of work and turnover intention is supported by the data.

Take in Table III

Conclusions and implications

The purpose of this study was to empirically investigate the relationship between the time demands of work, job satisfaction and turnover intention. It was found that the time demands of work significantly negatively associated with job satisfaction while significantly positively associated with turnover intention. Further, job satisfaction significantly negatively associated with turnover intention. With regard to the test of job satisfaction as a mediator in the relationship between the time demands of work and turnover intention, findings support for such mediation. Job satisfaction partially mediates the relationship between time demands of work and turnover intention. Therefore, the results of the study suggest that the increased levels of voluntary working time extensions of software developers to fulfil daily workloads could lead to decrease in job satisfaction, which subsequently could lead to increase turnover intention. This supports the arguments made by previous researchers that employee perceptions towards the time demands of work will influence their feeling of job satisfaction (e.g. Skinner and Pocock, 2008; Thornthwaite, 2004; Wallace, 1997) and in turn influence their decisions to stay or leave the industry (e.g. Byrd et al., 2000; Smits et al., 1993).

The industry workforce statistics of Sri Lanka suggests that the average length of employment with a single firm for an IT worker is three years and employee turnover rate is 9.7 per cent (SLICTA, 2007). Therefore, the results of this study imply that a greater understanding of employee turnover intentions might be gained by investigating the time demands of work.

In this regard, Perlow (2001) comments that the long hours of work are not inherent in the work of offshore software development; rather, work-time standards and norms are found to vary across countries, and the most important factor in determining workplace schedules is the management decisions. Therefore, the findings of the current study also imply the need of future investigations on the antecedents of time demands of work for

software developers in the offshore outsourced software development sector to identify mechanisms for minimising the time demands of work.

Organisations operating in the context of offshore outsourcing are continually trying to introduce value-added initiatives to strategically enhance the performance of their organisations and employees. For instance, Wickramasinghe and Jayabandu (2007) suggests that employees attached to the firms that provide flexible work hours experience a lower level of stress, feels less restriction at work, and helps to balance work and social life. Further, Altavilla et al. (2007) raise the question “how many hours per week should workers spend at their paying jobs?”, and they showed the importance of addressing this question by constructing policymakers’ reaction functions that are capable of modelling the optimal length of working time as a function of the relevant labour market variables. Therefore, by better understanding issues related to the time demands of work, human resource professionals can contribute to the strategic development of policies, practices, and programmes to foster greater job satisfaction and employee retention.

Finally, it should be noted that the author has not come across previous survey-based studies conducted in the offshore context that investigated the links proposed in this study to make straight forward comparisons. Therefore, considerable future research is necessary to validate the links suggested in this study. The current study represents a step in that direction.

Limitations and areas for future research

The data were collected from a considerably large homogeneous sample of software developers attached to OOSDF in Sri Lanka. The study relied on self-reported data. Therefore, future research studies in different samples and longitudinal studies are necessary that compliment questionnaire surveys with interviews and secondary data to validate the links proposed in this study. The review of literature (e.g. Müller and Wyss, 2007; Wise et al., 2007) suggests the influence of working time on work-life balance of

employees, hence, future studies could incorporate such variables to investigate whether working time influences the work-life balance of software developers attached to OOSDF.

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Figure

Figure 1. Job satisfaction as a mediator in the time demands of work– turnover intention relationship

Tables

Table I: Time demands of work

	Mean	SD
1 Usually, I work more hours, some times until late in the night	3.97	.68
2 Usually, I come to work on week ends, sometimes both Saturday and Sunday	3.68	.72
3 Usually, I take office work home when I leave the office, which I couldn't complete during the day	3.84	.81

Table II: Means, standard deviations and zero-order correlations

	Mean	SD	1	2	3	4	5
1 Gender	.62	.49	1				
2 Marital status	.27	.44	-.042	1			
3 Tenure	3.35	1.55	.112	.263**	1		
4 Time demands of work	3.82	.74	.157	-.119	.062	1	
5 Job satisfaction	3.77	.93	-.141	-.024	-.142	-.263**	1
6 Turnover intention	3.71	.91	.167	-.009	.085	.384**	-.656**

** significant at the 0.01 level (1-tailed).

Table III: Summarised results: job satisfaction as a mediator in the time demands of work and turnover intention relationship

Step	Variable	B	S.E.	β	R ² (Adj.)	F
1	<i>Controls</i> ^a					
	Gender	.295	.194	.158	.001	1.03
	Marital status	-.044	.218	-.022		
	Tenure	.043	.063	.033		
2	Time demands of work → Turnover intention	.451	.118	.376***	.132	4.56**
3	Time demands of work → Job satisfaction	-.318	.124	-.261*	.061	2.53*
4	Time demands of work → Turnover intention	.267	.097	.222**	.452	16.48***
	Job satisfaction → Turnover intention	-.578	.079	-.589***		

Sobel test $t = 2.42$ ($p = .015$)

Aroian test $t = 2.40$ ($p = .016$)

Goodman test $t = 2.44$ ($p = .014$)

Direct effect $\beta = .222$, Indirect effect $\beta = .162$

Note: * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$.

^a Control variables were retained in the subsequent steps of 2, 3, and 4.